

FOREIGN TRADE DURING THE REIGN OF SHAHRUKH MIRZA

Muazzamkhon Makhmudova

Senior Lecturer of the Department of World History
of Fergana State University, PhD

maxmudovamuazzam1982@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15754284>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada temuriy hukmdorlar Shohrux Mirzo va Mirzo Ulug'bek hukmronligi davrida tashqi savdo va diplomatik aloqalarning yuksak darajada rivojlanganligi yoritiladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Shohrux Mirzo, Mirzo Ulug'bek, Buyuk Ipak Yo'li, savdo aloqalari, diplomatik aloqalar.

Аннотация: В этой статье освещается высокий уровень развития внешней торговли и дипломатических отношений во время правления тимуридских правителей Шахруха Мирзы и Мирзы Улугбека.

Ключевые слова: Шахрух Мирзо, Мирзо Улугбек, Великий шелковый путь, торговые отношения, дипломатические отношения.

Annotation: This article illuminates the high level of development in foreign trade and diplomatic relations during the reign of Timurid rulers Shahrukh Mirzo and Mirzo Ulugbek.

Key words: Shahrukh Mirza, Mirzo Ulugbek, the Great Silk Road, trade relations, diplomatic relations.

Central Asia has long served as a crucial geographical region connecting East and West. During the Timurid era, international trade routes expanded and were strengthened. In this period, the importance of the Great Silk Road remained very high. Through these trade routes, products such as leather, silk, porcelain, tea, spices, precious stones, rubies, and diamonds were brought to the markets of Central Asia.

During the reign of Shahrukh Mirzo (1409-1447), the process of economic development intensified further. Particularly in cities, craftsmanship and trade sectors developed rapidly. In cities such as Herat, Merv, Balkh, and Bukhara, markets were expanded, and specialized trading stalls were established. In the markets of Herat, individual products - rare items, works of art, and high-quality handicrafts - were offered for sale, indicating the beginning of a new stage in the city's economic life[1].

Shahrukh Mirza recognized trade as one of the main factors in the prosperity and well-being of society. During his tenure, great importance was attached to road construction, the development of trade networks, and security issues. It was during this period that the Timurid state established active

political and economic relations with the countries of the Far and Near East - China, India, Iran, Russia, the Volga region, Siberia, and European countries - Spain, France, and England. This indicates the active participation of the Timurid state in the international trade arena and the implementation of an open market policy[2].

Cheap yarn, silk, cotton products, as well as finished fabrics, paper, dried fruits, and rice were exported from Herat to Russia, Tatarstan, and Siberia. Spanish Ambassador Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo, in his diaries, emphasized the important role of Samarkand in foreign trade. According to it, leather goods, including dyed gloves, were imported from Russia and Tatarstan, while fine royal fabrics, satins, musk, rubies, diamonds, and other precious stones, pearls, and medicinal plants were imported from China[3].

Also, the most delicate fragrant spices - nutmeg, cinnamon, mint, natural dyes, and other unique products - were brought to Herat from India. Such extensive trade relations during the Timurid era made Central Asia one of the economic and cultural centers of its time.

The embassies established by the Timurids played a crucial role in expanding trade with foreign states. Shahrukh Mirza and his son Mirza Ulugbek regularly exchanged ambassadors between their countries and China. Naturally, China had a vested interest in trading with the Timurids. Horses were primarily imported to China from Transoxiana and Khorasan. Merchants and ambassadors from Samarkand would journey to China (Beijing) once every two or three years, while Chinese merchants made regular visits to Samarkand and Herat.

In 1418, the ambassadors of Shahrukh Mirza and Ardashir were in China. The following year, Li Di and Chong-Ku came from China as ambassadors to Samarkand and Herat. They sent letters and valuable gifts to Shahrukh Mirza and Mirza Ulugbek as a symbol of strengthening friendly relations[4].

Shahrukh Mirza, considering the long-term prospects of the country, paid special attention to strengthening diplomatic relations with the rulers of China and India. Ambassadors of these states were received as official guests in Samarkand and Herat. In turn, representatives of Shahrukh, including the famous artist and diplomat Ghiyasuddin Naqqash, were sent to China, and ambassadors led by Abdurazak Samarkandi were sent to India. These diplomatic visits served to strengthen bilateral political and trade ties[5].

There were two major caravan routes from Transoxiana to China. The first route passed through the cities of Tashkent, Sayram, Semirechye, Turfan (Eastern Turkestan) and Kumul, while the second passed through the cities of

Khujand, Kokand, Margilan, Andijan, Osh, and the Alay Valley, passing through the cities of Kashgar, Khotan, and Yarkand in the Fergana Valley. The safety and stability of these trade routes were kept under special control by Shahrukh Mirza and his descendant Mirza Ulugh Beg[6]. At the beginning of the 15th century, neighborly relations with Tibet and India also strengthened, which was important for regional security and economic cooperation.

According to Abdurrazzaq Samarkandi, a merchant repeatedly took fabrics brought from China to Egypt and Anatolia, and the products he received from there were taken back to China. During the reign of Shahrukh Mirza, the distance between Egypt and China seemed to have shortened, indicating the safe and active operation of trade routes[7].

Moreover, caravans of 15-20 thousand camels arrived in Herat annually, bringing with them silk, sugar, and spices. Caravans also came from places such as Fergana, Turkestan, Samarkand, Bukhara, Balkh, Hissar, and Badakhshan, and Khorasan, Iraq, Rum, and Chinese goods could be found here[8].

In conclusion, it can be said that Shahrukh Mirza, as the successor of Amir Timur, paid special attention to trade and economics. He occupies an important place in history not only as a great commander and statesman, but also as a patron of culture and science. The activities of Shahrukh demonstrate that justice, science, and culture are powerful tools. Shahrukh Mirza also continued the policy of protecting merchants.

References:

1. To'xtiyev I. Temur va temuriylar sulolasining tangalari. – Toshkent:“Fan”, 1992. – B. 87.
2. Абдураимов М.А. Очерки аграрных отношений в Бухарском ханстве в XVI – первой половине XIX вв. Том 1. – Ташкент, 1966. – С. 63.
3. Muhammadjonov A. Temur va temuriylar saltanati. Tarixiy ocherk. – Toshkent, 1996. – B. 73.
4. Bo'riyev O. Temuriylar davri yozma manbalarida Markaziy Osiyo tarixiy geografiyasi. – Toshkent: Mumtoz so'z, 2017. – B. 221.
5. Уринбоев А., Буриев О. Фиёсиддин Наққошнинг Хитой сафарномаси. – Toshkent, 1991. – B. 6.
6. Hasanov H. Sayyoh olimlar. – Toshkent, 1981. – B. 22.
7. Беленицкий А.М. К вопросу о социальных отношениях в Иране в Хулагуидскую эпоху// Советскоевостоковедение. V. – Москва-Ленинград: Изд. АН СССР, 1948. – С. 118.
8. İsmail Aka. Mirza Şahruh Timur'un Hükümdar Oğlu, Uluğ Bey'in Babası 1405-1447. – İstanbul: Kronik Kitap, 2022. – S. 336.

